

The Future of the Relationship between Satellite TV Channels and Social Media

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Since the launch of the first satellite television station in the world in 1926, which is currently known as the NBC network, television has removed all competitors from the traditional media, known as mass media such as radio, print newspapers, and cinema.

But after the advent of the Internet in the second half of the twentieth century, and its availability to the entire world in the late twenty-first century, the Internet was able in the beginning of the twenty-first century to be a strong competitor to television through the emergence of social media platforms, the first of which was Facebook, which was launched in 2004.

The relationship between television channels and social media has begun to grow, as the latter has been able to capture the largest amount of audience, and this relationship has also taken the form of influence and influence, and may reach mutual giving, as television supplies its studio with the production of visual content ready to be published through social media, while these means give feedback by the public on everything that is broadcast through its platforms.

Therefore, to keep pace with the event from the beginning, NBC and Microsoft opened an interactive channel, MSNBC, in 1996, which is interactive by creating an interactive model between the Internet and television.

To demonstrate this in the Arab world, freelance journalist Mohammed Al-Rajawi conducted a master's thesis on the impact of social media on the reality of television in Yemen, which has 30 TV stations between government, partisan, and independent.

With the government's tightening of control over these stations, and during the events of the so-called Arab Spring that began in early 2010, a wide range of Yemenis tended to use social media platforms, especially Facebook, to broadcast images of protests and express their views. The number of its users currently reached 3564800. Satellite stations only directed their efforts to absorb this momentum through their stations through television programs dedicated to monitoring trends and opinions on social media, as well as programs concerned with publishing clips broadcast on social media.

The Internet usage statistics monitored by the Internet World Stats platform of the Miniwatts Marketing Group for market research and electronic platforms, which was established in 2001, will find that the number of Yemenis who are currently using the Internet has reached 8243772 browsers.

The study of Mohammed Al-Rajawi brings to mind the term "citizen journalism", which has been active in the Arab world since 2010, as it allowed communication between the media and citizens in a country to publish events through social media, such as:

Panorama Syria News Group, and Syrian news activists, because Syria is going through simultaneous conflicts with the regime's closure of international media offices.

The professor of media and communication at the University of Constantine in Algeria also sees Dr. Miloud Ahmed said that social media abolished the theory of the "gatekeeper" and the "magic bullet" that was hanging over the television media scene as a result of censorship by governments, but the researcher believes through his previous research in this field that the degree of abolition of the theory reaches "to some extent" because the television channels themselves turned to working with this theory in publishing what they like from social media, according to their media policy.

The audience of social media remains in control of what they want to watch from the videos, and the choice of time for that, which made the television stations forced to download most of their visual productions on social media, and about that, the former secretary of the Kuwaiti Journalists Association, Faisal Al-Qinai, states - in a report prepared by the Kuwaiti newspaper Al-Qabas - that the spread of YouTube channels has made a qualitative leap in the delivery of visuals in a simple and fast manner without the commitment of viewers to a specific time to watch.

In the same report, the Professor of Media and Public Relations at Kuwait University, Dr. Hussein Ibrahim, Professor of Media and Culture at Kuwait University Dr. Haneen Al-Ghabra that the Netflix platform has attracted a lot of the current generation to follow it at the expense of traditional media; due to what Netflix allows to follow according to the geographical scope with its programs and movies.

At the conclusion of the report, the Professor of Modern Communication and Media Science at Kuwait University, Dr. Bashayer Al-Sanea What the Yemeni researcher Mohammed Al-Rajawi sees in his letter that the future of the relationship between television and social media will acquire the status of "integration" according to Al-Sanea's description, and integration"according to Al-Rajawi's description, and both terms refer to or the relationship will continue to be affected and influenced.

The presence of the live broadcast feature in some social media applications has reduced the costs of hosting guests via satellite, or reaching them through correspondents in countries where the channel does not have offices. The simplest and most famous example is the conversation of Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan on the eve of the coup that took place in July 2016. He spoke through the FaceTime application of the Turkish-language broadcaster CNN. Some international satellite channels also communicate with their correspondents in Syria through Skype, as happened with the Al-Jazeera network in the early events of Syria that erupted in 2011.

In contrast, the relationship of influence that occurred between the two means led to the flow of some misleading information to the world of television, given the direct quotation without examining the materials published on social media, some users of which may be inclined to deep falsify what they publish.

The simplest example that was identified in 2020 was the achievement of publishing part of it as a video clip on the Yemeni Sadaqah platform to combat rumors entitled "The Frozen Dollar", in which the promotion of the counterfeit dollar was tracked under the last name. Unfortunately, there are television channels that circulate this term as a fact¹, such as the Egyptian eXtra news channel², the Syrian Orient channel³, the Al-Jazeera network⁴, the Lebanese Al-Jadeed channel, and other channels that published about this matter without referring for once to officials of the US Treasury Department or the Federal Bank to refute such matters.

The investigation was conducted in cooperation with the Arab Network for Information Auditors, and by publishing the Yemeni Sadaq platform, as it was found that the dollar broadcast through social media, and people are falsified assets of the Institute of Presidents Saddam Hussein and Muammar Gaddafi, is nothing but a counterfeit dollar that trapped many victims who spoke to the media about incidents of financial fraud they were exposed to. By investigating this matter, it becomes clear that there is a clear counterfeit of the currency, in addition to the incorrectness of this when referring to the guide of the Federal Bank on the currency of the US dollar, and issuing a smartphone application that reveals the dollar registered with the bank from the counterfeit dollar, in addition to the fact that the US dollar currency maintains its value since the first banknote minted after the establishment of the United States of America, in 1792.

The relationship between television and social media has also enhanced the emergence of mobile journalism and English-language knowledge of the term "moo-joo", short for the first two words, Mobile Journalism, where dedicated applications are used to record and edit videos and audio, as well as Photoshop.

The emergence of this type of journalism has made it possible for some channels to provide their reporters with a mobile studio to be able to cover the event, and this does

¹ - Source: eXtra news YouTube channel, link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iOm1b0PVmWU>

² - Source: Orient YouTube channel, link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E7TzaBAjgWQ>

³ - Source: Al Jazeera Network, Link: <https://www.aljazeera.net/ebusiness/2022/1/12/%8A%D8%BBA%D9%D8%B1-%D9%85%D8%B1%D8%AE%D8%B5-%8A%D9%88%D9%D8%AD%D8%A7%D8%B3%D8%A8-%8A%D8%B9%D9%84%D9%87-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%82%D8%A7%D9%86%D9%88%D9%86-%D9%85%D8%B9%D9%84%D9%88%D9%85%D8%A7%D8%AA>

⁴ - Source: Al-Jadeed YouTube channel, link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tIPFvGVok5A>

not cost more than \$150, including sound, lighting and stability equipment; an external plastic, and a tripod, to cover sudden incidents, as the journalist Siobhan Heanue created when she quickly covered the Australian fires in 2014, and also helps journalists keep themselves safe while taking pictures in riots and demonstrations. In this atmosphere, journalists can take pictures with caution, which Nick Garnett, the BBC editor, did while covering the riots in Manchester in 2011.

Finally, to address this relationship from the perspective of the first established channel in the world, the head of the NBC Universal Research Center points out that the viewing rates of television channels are not affected by social media, as Wertzels cites a study prepared by the American company Comcast for satellite broadcasting, telecommunications services, and the Internet,⁵ which jointly manages the NBC Universal group.

This study, which was conducted in 2014 during the start of the Olympic Games in the Russian city of Sochi, concluded that 19% of viewers talked about the events that lasted for 18 days and an average of 1,500 hours of viewing on social media platforms, which means that an additional 150 million people were exposed to these conversations on Facebook and 23 million on Twitter, compared to 21 million TV viewers per day during the Olympic Games, according to the American Financial Times.

Therefore, we find that all the previous indications mentioned indicate that the future of television will remain complementary and in harmony with social media, and it is no wonder that radio has withstood until the moment of the emergence of "podcasts", and the same is true for television. Both television and social media have used their technologies to serve each other, from production to broadcasting and archiving, but it should be said that the future of satellites is at stake due to this, and we will find a future orientation for satellites towards the provision of industrial Internet service to keep pace with the digital world that is imposing its presence in every technology industry.

⁵ Source: Comcast, link: <https://corporate.comcast.com/news-information/news-feed/sochi-2014-a-tv-everywhere-success-story>.

Sources

Al-Baiti, Hassan. (2022 Nov 2). The truth of the so-called frozen dollar. The Yemeni Sidq platform. Retrieved from link:

<https://sidqyem.com/?s=389>

Milhoud, Murad. (2021 Dec 24). The impact of social media platforms on the production of television image and visual speech carrying security information . I want scientific platform. Retrieved from link:

<https://cutt.us/0skEp>

Al Qabas Kuwaiti Newspaper. (2020 Jan 16). Television.. Is he nearing extinction? Retrieved from link:

<https://www.alqabas.com/article/5743461>

Alragawi, Mohammed. (2018). Social media impact on television in Yemen: the case of belqeess tv. Istanbul; Türkiye: Kadir Has University. Retrieved from:

https://www.academia.edu/40981142/SOCIAL_MEDIA_IMPACT_ON_TELEVISION_IN_YEMEN_THE_CASE_OF_BELQEES_TV

Steel, Emily. (2014 April 27). Social media not yet a 'game changer' for boosting TV viewership. The Financial Times. Retrieved from:

<https://www.ft.com/content/1ac5e370-cbfc-11e3-a934-00144feabdc0>

Nbc Universal. (No Date). History of NBC. Retrieved from:

<https://www.nbcuniversal.com/history#start>

Internet World Stats. (No Date). Static of Middle East. Retrieved from:

<https://www.internetworldstats.com/middle.htm#ye>